

Fast RLS Adaptive Algorithms of Quadratic Volterra ADF

Jinhui Chao, Tomonori Kubota and Shinpei Uno

Dept. of Electrical and Electronic Eng., Faculty of Science and Eng., Chuo University
1-13-27, Kasuga, Bunkyo, Tokyo 112-8551, Japan
e-mail : jchao@elect.chuo-u.ac.jp

ABSTRACT

It is shown in [6] that quadratic Volterra adaptive filters (ADF) have error surfaces which are always extremely steep on only one particular direction but relatively flat on the other directions. This explains the instability in the learning processing of Volterra ADF and implies unavoidable slow convergence of traditional gradient adaptive algorithms. On the other hand, the RLS algorithm for Volterra ADF costs $O(N^4)$ multiplications where N is the number of linear terms in Volterra ADF. This paper shows a new algorithm for Gaussian input signals which converges in the same rate as RLS but costs only $O(N^2)$ multiplications which is the same as the LMS algorithm. This algorithm is based on a complete analysis of the intrinsic geometry of the error surface for white input signals and whitening operation of any colored input signals. Simulations shown that this algorithm works well even in non-Gaussian input cases.

1 Introduction

Among numerous models of nonlinear systems, the so-called Volterra filters are based expansion of general nonlinear functionals thus can represent arbitrary systems with sufficient many terms. Moreover, Volterra adaptive filters (ADF) are known belong to a class of nonlinear ADF which are of parameter-linear, i.e., by definition, their outputs are nonlinear functionals of the input signals but linear functionals of the system parameters. This important property thus guarantees convexity of the mean-square-error surface in their adaptive learning, therefore global convergence of the gradient or Newton-Raphson adaptive algorithms widely used for linear ADF. This unusual feature makes the Volterra ADF much preferable to other models of nonlinear ADF including neural networks suffered from the local minima problem. Recently Volterra ADF have been successfully applied to echo cancellation, automatic equalization and other nonlinear systems[1].

However, it is shown in [6] that quadratic Volterra ADF have some quite nontrivial geometric feature of their error surfaces. i.e. The error surface is always extremely steep on only one particular direction but rel-

atively flat on the other directions. More specifically, the curvature on the steepest direction of the error surface is always in order of N times the curvatures on the rest directions, where N is the number of linear terms in Volterra ADF. This explains the often-observed instability in the learning processing of Volterra ADF. In order to guarantee the convergence and to obtain numerical stability, one has to use very small stepsize in adaptation to avoid overshoot, this means slow convergence of traditional gradient adaptive algorithms is unavoidable.

On the other hand, the fastest adaptive algorithm, the Newton-Raphson or RLS algorithm for a quadratic Volterra ADF will cost $O(N^4)$ multiplications, since it needs iterative operation to inverse the $N^2 \times N^2$ covariance matrix of the input signal where N is the number of linear terms, much beyond the capability of on-line processing available presently.

In this paper, we show a new algorithm with the same convergent rate of the RLS algorithm and the same cost as the gradient algorithms such as the LMS algorithm. This algorithm is based on a complete eigen-analysis of covariance matrices of Gaussian white input signals, which reveals also intrinsic geometry the error surface. Thus a fast algorithm for such input signals are shown with cost of $O(N^2)$. This algorithm is then applied to colored input signals by iterative whitening operation. Since it is enough to apply this whitening operation only to the linear terms of the input signal, the cost remains $O(N^2)$. In the sequel, the whole computational cost of the algorithm is of $O(N^2)$, the same as gradient algorithms such as the LMS algorithm. Convergence performance of the proposed algorithm is approved by computer simulations. Moreover, simulations are also carried out to apply the algorithm to several non-Gaussian input cases. Similar fast convergence performance is also observed in these cases, which may suggest certain generalization of the theoretical analysis on the error surfaces and applicability of the fast algorithm for general inputs with symmetric probability distributions.

It is interesting to notice that this kind of whitening operations has been used in linear ADF to accelerate the convergence for colored input signals, and treatment for

white input signals is trivial since their error surface is a uniformly curved bowl, or their covariance matrices are constant multiples of the identity matrix [2]. On the other hand, the white input case becomes much more nontrivial for Volterra ADF due to complicated geometry of their error surface. In fact, the whitening operation has also been applied to Volterra ADF to reduce the computation cost of RLS algorithm [4]. Since the one-direction crashed shape of the error surface, or quantitatively the order of the condition number of the covariance matrix is the same for either white or colored input signal, a complete understanding of eigen-construction of the covariance matrix is required in order to achieve fast convergence using whitening operation.

2 Volterra ADF algorithms

Suppose a quadratic Volterra ADF have N linear terms and N^2 quadratic terms. The input signal vector to the linear terms is defined as

$$\mathbf{x}_n = [x_n, x_{n-1}, \dots, x_{n-N+1}]^T.$$

The covariance matrix of $\mathbf{x}_n$ is $\mathbf{R}_{xx} = E[\mathbf{x}_n \mathbf{x}_n^T]$.

Including the quadratic terms, the total input signal vector is of $N(N+1)$ dimension:

$$\mathbf{X}_n = [x_n^T, x_n x_n^T, x_{n-1} x_n^T, \dots, x_{n-N+1} x_n^T]^T = \mathbf{x}_n \otimes \mathbf{x}_n.$$

The covariance matrix of total input signal vector $\mathbf{X}_n$ is defined as

$$\mathbf{R}_{xx} = E[\mathbf{X}_n \mathbf{X}_n^T] = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{xx} & \mathbf{O} \\ \mathbf{O} & \mathcal{Q} \end{bmatrix}$$

Denote the coefficient of ADF as $\mathbf{W}_n$, the output of the ADF is $y_n = \mathbf{W}_n^T \mathbf{X}_n$

Denote the error between unknown system output d_n and y_n as e_n , the optimal coefficient vector as $\mathbf{W}$, the covariance of observation noise as σ_{noise} . The mean-square-error function

$$E(e_n^2) = (\mathbf{W} - \mathbf{W}_n)^T \mathbf{R}_{xx} (\mathbf{W} - \mathbf{W}_n) + \sigma_{noise}^2$$

is a upper-convex parabolic hypersurface whose principal axes and principal curvatures are the eigenvectors and eigenvalues of $\mathbf{R}_{xx}$.

A gradient adaptive algorithm for Volterra ADF such as the LMS algorithm as below costs $O(N^2)$ multiplications for each update.

$$\mathbf{W}_{n+1} = \mathbf{W}_n + \mu e_n \mathbf{X}_n$$

(μ is the stepsize).

The Newton-Raphson or RLS algorithm as below costs $O(N^4)$ multiplications for each update.

$$\mathbf{W}_{n+1} = \mathbf{W}_n + \mu e_n \mathbf{R}_{xx}^{-1} \mathbf{X}_n$$

3 Analysis of Error surface

Theorem 1 [6] *For quadratic Volterra ADF with a Gaussian input signal, the maximal eigenvalue λ_1 of $\mathbf{R}_{xx}$ is always $O(N)$ times of the rest nonzero eigenvalues. i.e. $\lambda_1 = O(N)\lambda_i, i > 1$*

Therefore, the error surface is always extremely steep on direction of ϕ_1 , the eigenvector corresponding to the maximal eigenvalue, but relatively flat on the other directions.

Theorem 2 *When the input is a white Gaussian signal with covariance σ_x , the complete eigenvalues $\{\lambda_k\}$ of $\mathbf{R}_{xx}$ are as follows:*

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1(\mathbf{R}_{xx}) &= (N+2)\sigma_x^4 \\ \lambda_k(\mathbf{R}_{xx}) &= 2\sigma_x^4, \quad k = 2, \dots, \frac{N^2+N}{2} \\ \lambda_k(\mathbf{R}_{xx}) &= \sigma_x^2, \quad k = \frac{N^2+N}{2} + 1, \dots, \frac{N^2+3N}{2} \\ \lambda_k(\mathbf{R}_{xx}) &= 0, \quad k = \frac{N^2+3N}{2} + 1, \dots, N^2 + N \end{aligned}$$

The complete eigenvectors $\{\phi_k\}$ of $\mathbf{R}_{xx}$ corresponding to λ_k are as follows.

$$\phi_1 = \sigma_x^4 \underbrace{(0, \dots, 0, 1, 0, \dots, 0, 0, 1, 0, \dots, 0, \dots, 0, 0, \dots, 1)}_{N(N+1)}$$

For $\lambda_k = \sigma_x^2$, $\{\phi_k, k = \frac{N^2+N}{2} + 1, \dots, \frac{N^2+N}{2} + N\}$, are an orthogonal basis of the N -dim. subspace of the input signal vector to the linear terms.

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{\frac{N^2+N}{2}+1} &= \sigma_x^2 \underbrace{(1, 0, 0, \dots, 0, 0, 0, \dots, 0)}_N \underbrace{(0, \dots, 0)}_{N^2} \\ \phi_{\frac{N^2+N}{2}+2} &= \sigma_x^2 \underbrace{(0, 1, 0, \dots, 0, 0, 0, \dots, 0)}_N \underbrace{(0, \dots, 0)}_{N^2} \\ &\dots \\ \phi_{\frac{N^2+N}{2}+N} &= \sigma_x^2 \underbrace{(0, 0, 0, \dots, 0, 1, 0, \dots, 0)}_N \underbrace{(0, \dots, 0)}_{N^2} \end{aligned}$$

For $\lambda_k = 2\sigma_x^4$, there is two patterns, when $k = 2, \dots, \frac{N^2+N}{2}$, the ϕ_k have all zero entries except that the $((k-1)N+i)$ -th and the $((i-1)N+k)$ -th entries equals 1. ($i = k+1, \dots, N, k = 1, \dots, N-1$).

$$\phi_k = \sigma_x^4 \underbrace{(0, \dots, 0)}_N \dots \underbrace{0, 1, 0}_{(k-1)N+i} \dots \underbrace{0, 1, 0}_{(i-1)N+k} \dots 0$$

The number of such eigenvectors is $(N^2 - N)/2 - 1$. The second pattern of the rest N ϕ_k have all zero entries except that the t -th entry equals 1.

$$\phi_k = \sigma_x^4 \underbrace{(0, \dots, 0)}_N, \dots, 0, \dots, 0, \underbrace{1}_t, 0, \dots, 0,$$

here $t \neq (k-1)N+i, t \neq (i-1)N+k$

Here the eigenvectors with zero eigenvalue are exactly the same form as in the first pattern of eigenvectors with eigenvalue $2\sigma_x^4$, except that one of the two nonzero entries, i.e. either the $((k-1)N+i)$ -th or the $((i-1)N+k)$ -th entry, equals -1 . e.g.

$$\phi_k = \sigma_x^4 \underbrace{(0, \dots, 0)}_N, \quad \underbrace{0, 1, 0, \dots, 0}_{(k-1)N+i}, \quad \underbrace{-1, 0, \dots, 0}_{(i-1)N+k}$$

The number of them is naturally $(N^2 - N)/2$.

Proof: In the first place, the eigenvectors with eigenvalue σ_x^2 are those span the eigenspace of $\mathbf{R}_{xx}$ and form an orthogonal basis of the N -dim subspace of the linear terms.

It is shown in [6] that in $\mathcal{R}_{xx}$ the submatrix $\mathcal{Q} = \mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B}$ where

$$\mathbf{A} = \sigma_x^4 (\mathbf{I}_{N^2} + \mathbf{P})$$

Here $\mathbf{I}_{N^2}$ is the $N^2 \times N^2$ identity matrix and $\mathbf{P}$ is a permutation matrix which can be decomposed into a product of transpositions. Denote the transposition or exchange of the i -th and j -th row vectors as (i, j) , then

$$\mathbf{P} = \prod_{k=1}^{N-1} \prod_{i=k+1}^N ((k-1)N+i, (i-1)N+k)$$

Here we used $\mathbf{R}_{xx} \otimes \mathbf{R}_{xx} = \sigma_x^4 \mathbf{I}_{N^2}$ and the k -th row vector of $\mathbf{R}_{xx}$ equals $\mathbf{r}_k = (\delta_{i,k} \mid i = 1, \dots, N)^T$ ($\delta_{a,b}$ is the Kronecker delta).

$$\mathbf{B} = \gamma \gamma^T$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma &= \text{Column}(\mathbf{R}_{xx}) = \sigma_x^2 \text{Column}(\mathbf{I}_{N^2}) \\ &= \sigma_x^2 (\delta_{i, k(N+1)+1}, k = 0, \dots, N-1)^T \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\mathbf{B}$ has the nonzero eigenvalue $\gamma^T \gamma = N\sigma_x^4$ with the eigenvector as γ .

Moreover, γ is P -invariant,

$$\mathbf{P}\gamma = \gamma.$$

This can be proved as follows. Supposed that there is nonzero entries of γ which are permuted by $\mathbf{P}$, then one of the indices of certain transposition in $\mathbf{P}$, either $(k-1)N+i$ or $(i-1)N+k$ has to be $l(N+1)+1$, the indices of nonzero entries in γ , or $k=i$, but it is obvious that $\mathbf{P}$ does not contain such transposition.

Thus the γ is an eigenvector of $\mathcal{Q}$ with the eigenvalue as $(N+2)\sigma_x^4$.

According to the theorem on boundaries of all the eigenvalues in [6], $\lambda_{max} = \lambda_1 \leq (N+2)\sigma_x^4$. Thus the eigenvalue of γ_1 is λ_1 the and $\sigma_x^4 \phi_1 = \gamma$.

Now we consider the rest eigenvectors, which must lie in the subspace orthogonal to ϕ_1 . Thus, instead of

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{Q} &= \sigma_x^4 (\mathbf{I}_{N^2} + \mathbf{P}) + \gamma \gamma^T \\ &= \sigma_x^4 (\mathbf{I}_{N^2} + \mathbf{P} + \phi_1 \phi_1^T) \end{aligned}$$

we can consider only the matrix $\mathbf{A} = \sigma_x^4 (\mathbf{I}_{N^2} + \mathbf{P})$. Thus the eigenvectors of $\mathbf{A}$ therefore the rest of $\mathcal{Q}$ are eigenvectors of $\mathbf{P}$ with eigenvalues as ± 1 .

If their eigenvalue with respect to $\mathbf{P}$ is 1, their eigenvalues with respect to $\mathcal{Q}$ are $2\sigma_x^4$. The number of these kind of eigenvector is $N(N+1)/2 - 1$.

If their eigenvalue with respect to $\mathbf{P}$ is -1 , their eigenvalue with respect to $\mathcal{Q}$ is 0, the number of such eigenvectors equals $N(N-1)/2$.

Since the sign of these eigenvectors are changed by $\mathbf{P}$, they must have the 1 and -1 as the only nonzero entries which are exchanged by each transpositions. This concludes the proof of the theorem. $\square$

4 Fast algorithm for white inputs

Algorithm 1 .

Step 1: Calculate the ϕ_i -components of the coefficient vector $\mathbf{W}_n$ and the total input signal vector $\mathbf{X}_n$ as

$$\mathbf{W}_n^i = \frac{\phi_i^T \mathbf{W}_n}{\phi_i^T \phi_i}, \quad \mathbf{X}_n^i = \frac{\phi_i^T \mathbf{X}_n}{\phi_i^T \phi_i}.$$

Step 2: Update the coefficient vector as

$$\mathbf{W}_{n+1}^i = \mathbf{W}_n^i + \mu \frac{1}{\lambda_i} e_n \mathbf{X}_n^i$$

Since along directions of each eigenvectors this algorithm uses the stepsizes which are reciprocal of the curvatures on the directions, or the eigenvalues of $\mathcal{R}_{xx}$, optimal convergence can be achieved without overshoot.

Below, we show that this algorithm is equivalent to the Newton-Raphson or RLS algorithm. Recall that the eigen-decomposition of $\mathcal{R}_{xx} = \Phi^T \Lambda \Phi$, where Φ has column vectors as the eigenvectors ϕ_i 's, and $\Lambda = \text{diag}\{\lambda_i\}$. The update formula can be transformed into

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi^T \mathbf{W}_{n+1} &= \Phi^T \mathbf{W}_n + \mu e_n \Lambda^{-1} \Phi^T \mathbf{X}_n \\ \mathbf{W}_{n+1} &= \mathbf{W}_n + \mu e_n \mathcal{R}_{xx}^{-1} \mathbf{X}_n. \end{aligned}$$

which is the RLS algorithm. In fact, the RLS algorithm needs to estimate $\mathcal{R}_{xx}^{-1}$ recursively so the convergence is deteriorated by estimation errors. Since we use true values of the eigenvalues and eigenvectors obtained exactly as in the Theorem 2, the above algorithm can always update with correct stepsizes and in correct directions so could be able to converge even faster.

Notice that due to the very sparse structure of the eigenvectors, the inner products and projections need only to choose entry indices which is almost free. Overall the algorithm costs the same computations as the LMS algorithm, which is of $O(N^2)$.

5 Fast algorithm for colored inputs

Algorithm 2 .

Step 1: Whiten the input signal x_n (linear terms) and

Figure 1: Convergence comparison for Gaussian inputs

denote the result as $\mathbf{u}_n$, use $\mathbf{u}_n$ instead of $\mathbf{x}_n$ to derive a new total input signal vector $\mathbf{X}_n$;

Step 2: Calculate the ϕ_i -components of $\mathbf{X}_n$ and $\mathbf{W}_n$;

$$\mathbf{W}_n^i = \frac{\phi_i^T \mathbf{W}_n}{\phi_i^T \phi_i}, \quad \mathbf{X}_n^i = \frac{\phi_i^T \mathbf{X}_n}{\phi_i^T \phi_i}$$

Step 3: Update the coefficient vector as

$$\mathbf{W}_{n+1}^i = \mathbf{W}_n^i + \mu \frac{1}{\lambda_i} e_n \mathbf{X}_n^i$$

The whitening filters could be an adaptive lattice filter or a linear predictor or the DCT if one prefers fast implementation and tolerates approximation errors. Since only whitening of the linear terms in the input signal is needed, even one uses the RLS algorithm in the lattice filter or the linear predictor which then implements our algorithm as an exact RLS algorithm for Volterra ADF, the cost of the whole algorithm still remains as $O(N^2)$.

6 Simulation results

Volterra ADF is assumed with $N=20$ linear terms, and 210 quadratic terms. The input signal x_n is a 15th order AR process which is generated from an all-pole filters with Gaussian white input ω_n such that covariance is $1/48$. An observation noise of -35 [dB] uncorrelated with the input signal is assumed. A gradient adaptive lattice filter is used as the whitening filter. The adaptive algorithm for PARCOR due to [7] is used. The convergence performances are compared between the proposed algorithm and the normalized LMS algorithm with whitened and unwhitened input signals, in Fig.1. It can be observed that the whitening alone does not improve much convergence of the NLMS algorithm.

It is also of great interest that if the algorithm can be applied to non-Gaussian inputs. We examined the cases

Figure 2: Convergence comparison for non-Gaussian inputs

using white input signals with non-Gaussian but symmetric distributions of probability. They are derived by addition of m white signals with identical uniform distribution on interval $[-1/2, 1/2]$. It is known that when m increases, the distribution of the summation will get closer to, and almost equals a Gaussian signal if $m \geq 12$. Therefore, these white signals are chosen also because m can be used as a measure of the deviation from the Gaussian distribution. For all cases for $m = 1, \dots, 12$, we observed fast performances of our algorithms similar to the Gaussian input case. In Fig.2, comparisons for three cases when $m = 2, 4, 10$ are shown between the proposed algorithm and the normalized LMS algorithm. One can observe that their convergences are quite indifferent to the shapes of distributions.

References

- [1] V. John Mathews, "Adaptive Polynomial Filters", IEEE SP Magazine, July, 1991.
- [2] Widrow, Stern, "Adaptive signal processing", 1985
- [3] C. W. Therrien, W. K. Jenkins, "New Insights in the Analysis of Polynomial Adaptive Filters", IEEE DSP Workshop, September, 1996.
- [4] W. K. Jenkins et al. "Advanced Concept in Adaptive Signal Processing", Kluwer, 1996.
- [5] J. Chao, A. Inomata, "A Convergence Analysis of Volterra Adaptive Filters", Proc. of ISCAS'97, Vol. IV, pp.2477-2480, 1997-6.
- [6] J. Chao, A. Inomata, S. Uno, "Convergence analysis and fast algorithms of Volterra adaptive filters", Proc. EUSIPCO'98, Sept. 1998.
- [7] J. Makhoul "Stable and efficient lattice digital filters: Properties and applications" IEEE Transactions on ASSP, 25, pp.423-428, Oct. 1977.